

A COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF JATYADI TAILAM

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ABSTRACT

In Ayurveda, *Sneha Kalpana* refers to the formulation and preparation of medicated fats or oils, typically using *grita* (ghee), *taila*(oil), *vasa*(animal fat), or *majja* (bone marrow) as the base and processed with medicinal drugs. These formulations are widely used for both internal (*abhyantara*) and external (*bahya*) therapeutic purposes. *Jatyadi taila* is a herbo-mineral formulation prescribed by many physicians for external application in *Vrana*. It is mentioned in various classical textbooks such as *Sharangadhara Samhita*, *Gada Nigraha*, *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*, *Bhavaprakasha*, *Vangasena Samhita*, *Yogaratanakara* etc. The first ingredient in this formulation is *Jati* (*Jasminum grandiflorum*). So it is called as *Jatyadi taila*. *Jati* is *tridosha samana* drug, *vatahara* because of *Ushna virya*, *pitta samaka* due to *Tikta kashaya rasa*, and *kapha samaka* due to *Ushna virya*, *katu vipaka* and *tikta kashaya rasa*. While

examining the formulation, it was observed that nearly all the ingredients have properties that help restore *tridosha* to its balanced state. On 15 references, it came to notice that the references, that are quoted in the *Sharangadhara Samhita*, *Bhaishajya Ratnavali vranasotha*, *Bhavaprakasha vranasotha*, *Yogaratanakara sadhyovrana* are the same. Yoga mentioned in *Bhavaprakasha*, *Vangasena samhitha*, *Yoga Ratnakara* are also the same and is explained in the context of *danta nadi* in *Mukharoga adhyaya*. This article brings together the introduction, materials and methods, method of preparation, references from various classical

texts, perspectives on the composition as interpreted by different Acharyas, a review of the drug, pharmacological properties of its ingredients, along with a discussion and conclusion.

KEYWORDS: *Jatyadi taila, Sneha Kalpana, Tridosha hara, Vrana, Mukha roga.*

INTRODUCTION

Sneha Kalpana, an oil-based preparation in Ayurvedic therapeutics, has been utilized for over five thousand years. Its primary purpose is to incorporate both water-soluble and fat-soluble medicinal components into a single dosage form, thereby offering a wide spectrum of therapeutic effects. *Acharya Sharangadhara* has described various stages of *Sneha paka* on the basis of mode of administration of *Sneha Kalpana*. These stages are mainly divided into three i.e *Mridu paka, Madhyama paka* and *Khara paka*. *Taila* prepared in *khara paka* stage is intended for external use, as it undergoes complete dehydration and achieves a consistency and potency suitable for topical application. *Jatyadi taila* is a classical Ayurvedic herbo-mineral formulation that comes under this category. *Jatyadi taila* contains about 18 drugs, including *tila taila, tutha* and popular for external application in the treatment of various skin and wound-related conditions. 15 references are available for *Jatyadi tailam*. But there is some difference in the ingredients and indications. Main indication includes *Vrana, Mukha roga, Bhagandhara, and Upadhamsa*. In this study, we mainly consider the reference from the *Sharangadhara Samhita*.^[1] Some of the other classical texts that quote about *Jatyadi taila* are *Gada nigraha, Yoga ratnakara, Bhavaprakasha, Vangasena Samhita, Brihat Nigandu Ratnakara, and Bhaishajya Ratnavali*. Most of the drugs in this preparation have *tikta* and *Kashaya rasa*, so it possesses *ropaka, vedanasthapana, and shothahara* properties. The objective of the present study is to collect and critically analyze the available classical references, highlighting both their similarities and differences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The information related to *Jatyadi taila* has been compiled from classical Ayurvedic texts and various reputable online sources. Relevant content has also been gathered from available Ayurvedic commentaries. For this study, the reference from the *Sharangadhara Samhita* has been selected as the primary source.

Table no. 1: Ingredients used for *Jatyadi tailam* preparation.

Sl no	Ingredients	Scientific name	Part used	Quantity
1.	<i>Jati</i>	<i>Jasminum grandiflorum</i>	Leaf	1/18 part
2.	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Leaf	1/18 part
3.	<i>Patola</i>	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>	Leaf/plant	1/18 part
4.	<i>Naktamala (Karanja)</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Leaf	1/18 part
5.	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Root	1/18 part
6.	<i>Kushta</i>	<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Root	1/18 part
7.	<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Rhizome	1/18 part
8.	<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Stem	1/18 part
9.	<i>Katurohini</i>	<i>Picorrhiza kurroa</i>	Rhizome	1/18 part
10.	<i>Manjishta</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	Root	1/18 part
11.	<i>Padmaka</i>	<i>Prunus cerasoides</i>	Heartwood	1/18 part
12.	<i>Lodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos racemose</i>	Stem bark	1/18 part
13.	<i>Abhaya</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Fruit	1/18 part
14.	<i>Nilotpala</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Flower	1/18 part
15.	<i>Sariva (sveta sariva)</i>	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Root	1/18 part
16.	<i>Naktamala</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Seed	1/18 part
17.	<i>Siktha(madhucchista)</i>			1/18 part
18.	<i>Tutthaka (Tutha)</i>			1/18 part
19.	<i>Taila (tila)</i>		Oil	4 part
20.	Water			16 part

Method of preparation

The general method of preparation of *Sneha Kalpana* involves heating a mixture of *kalka*, *Sneha dravya* and *drava dravya* in a proportion of ¼:1:4, respectively. In this, the ingredients mentioned in table no.1 from 1 to 16 (except *madhucchista* and *tuttha*) are made into *kalka* form and mixed with 4 parts of *tila taila*, and 16 parts of *drava*, in a wide-mouthed bronze vessel. The mixture is then heated over a mild fire. Continuous stirring is essential to prevent sticking at the bottom of the vessel. Heating was continued till it attained *khara paka* (*lakshana*-hard to touch, all the liquid part evaporates and possible to make *varti* but it breaks soon). The oil is filtered while hot using a muslin cloth into a beaker containing powdered *tutha* and thin-sliced *madhucchista* (*patra paka*). Stir till it dissolves completely. When it gets cool, store in an airtight container.

RESULTS

Table no. 2: Reference from different classical texts.

Sl.no	Classical text	Name of yoga	Adhyaya	Rogadhikara
1	<i>Gada nigraha</i> ^[2]	<i>Jatyadi taila</i>	<i>Taila prakarana</i>	<i>Sannipatha jwara</i>
2	<i>Gada nigraha</i> ^[3]	<i>Jatyadi taila</i>	<i>Upadamsadhikara</i>	<i>Upadamsham</i>
3	<i>Bhaishajya ratnavali</i> ^[4]	<i>Jatyadi taila</i>	<i>Vranasotha chikitsa</i>	
4	<i>Bhaishajya ratnavali</i> ^[5]	<i>Jatyadi taila</i>	<i>Mukha roga chikitsa</i>	

5	Yogaratanakara ^[6]	Jatyadi tailam	Sadhyovrana chikitsa	
6	Yogaratanakara ^[7]	Jatyadi tailam	Mukha roga	Dhantagata roga
7	Bhavaprakasa ^[8]	Jatyadi tailam	Vrana sotha chikitsa	
8	Bhavaprakasa ^[9]	Jatyadi tailam	Mukha roga chikitsa	Dhantanadi rogam
9	Sharangadhara Samhita	Jatyadi tailam	Taila prakarana	
10	Vangasena Samhita ^[10]	Jatyadi tailam	Mukha roga	Dantagata rogam

Table no. 3: Ingredients of *Jatyadi taila* in various classical textbooks.

Sl no	Ingredients	B.R (Mukha roga)	Sh.sa/ B.R(vranasotha)/ B.P(vranasotha)/ Y.R (sadhyovrana)	Y.R(Mukha roga)/ B.P/ Van.Sa	G.Ni (Taila)	G.Ni (Upadamsa)	B.Ni.R (Kshudra roga)
1	Jati	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Nimba		✓				
3	Patola		✓				
4	Naktamala (Karanja)		✓				✓
5	Madhuka	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
6	Kushta	✓	✓				
7	Haridra	✓	✓		✓	✓	
8	Daruharidra	✓	✓		✓		
9	Katurohini		✓				
10	Manjishta		✓	✓	✓		
11	Padmaka		✓				
12	Lodhra	✓	✓	✓			
13	Abhaya	✓	✓				
14	Nilotpala	✓	✓				
15	Sariva (sveta sariva)		✓		✓		
16	Siktha(madhucchista)		✓				
17	Tutthaka (Tuttha)		✓				
18	Jeevaka				✓		
19	Rishabhaka				✓		
20	Rasna				✓		
21	Saralam				✓		
22	Devadaru				✓		
23	Musta	✓			✓		
24	Taleesa				✓		
25	Pata				✓		
26	Varuna				✓		✓
27	Chitraka				✓		✓
28	Kubja				✓		
29	Sarvasuganda				✓		
30	Krishna sariva				✓		
31	Anantha				✓		
32	Amalaki	✓			✓		
33	Murva				✓		
34	Karaveerakam				✓		✓
35	Deva pushpa				✓		

36	Sirisa				✓		
37	Syonaka				✓		
38	Chavya	✓			✓		
39	Laksha				✓		
40	Ksheera kakoli				✓		
41	Madana			✓			
42	Kantaki			✓			
43	Swadu kantaki			✓			
44	Khadira	✓		✓			
45	Dugdhi					✓	
46	Visala					✓	
47	Sankupushpi	✓					
48	Bakula	✓					
49	Amra beeja	✓					
50	Vibhitaki	✓					
51	Sunti	✓					
52	Maricha	✓					
53	Pippali	✓					
54	Valakam	✓					
55	Sindoora (Girisindoora)	✓					
56	Swarna gairiakm	✓					
57	Vatangura	✓					
58	Loha choorna	✓					
59	Tila taila	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

G.Ni- Gada nigraha, Y.R-Yoga ratnakara, B.P-Bhavaprakasha, Van.sa-Vangasena Samhita, B.Ni.R-Brihat Nigandu Ratnakara, B.R-Bhaishajya Ratnavali, Sh.sa-Sharangadhara Samhita.

Table no. 4: Pharmacodynamic properties of Jatyadi taila.

Sl.no	Drugs	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Doshagnata	Karma
1	Jati	Tikta kashaya	Laghu, snigdha, mridu	Ushna	Katu	Tridosha samaka	Vishagna, kushtagna, vrananasana
2	Nimba	Tikta kashaya	Laghu, ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	Pitta kapha samana	Krimighna, vishagna, vranaghna
3	Patola	Tikta	Laghu, snigdha	Ushna	Katu	Tridosha samana	Kushtagna, kandughna
4	Naktamala (Karanja)	Katu, Tikta kashaya	Laghu, tikshna	Ushna	Katu	Vata kapha samana	Jantugna, sothahara, vranaropaka
5	Madhuka	Madhura	Guru, snigdha	Sheeta	madhura	Vata pitta samaka	Vranahara, raktapittahara
6	Kushta	Tikta, katu, madhura	Laghu, ruksha,	Ushna	Katu	Kaphavata samaka	Visagna, sothahara,

			<i>Tikshna</i>				<i>kushtagna</i>
7	<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Tikta katu</i>	<i>Laghu, ruksha,</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kapha pitta samaka</i>	<i>Varnya, vranahara, kandugna</i>
8	<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, ruksha,</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pitta kapha samana</i>	<i>Raktasodaka, vranahara</i>
9	<i>Katurohini</i>	<i>tikta</i>	<i>Ruksha, laghu</i>	<i>sheeta</i>	<i>katu</i>	<i>Pitta samaka</i>	<i>Arsogna, kushtagna, krimigna</i>
10	<i>Manjishtha</i>	<i>Tikta Kashaya, madhura</i>	<i>Guru, ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pitta kapha samaka</i>	<i>Raktha sodhaka, sothahara, vranahara</i>
11	<i>Padmaka</i>	<i>Tikta kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pitta kapha samaka</i>	<i>Vranahara, twakdoshanasaka, vishahara</i>
12	<i>Lodhra</i>	<i>Kashaya,</i>	<i>Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pitta kapha samaka</i>	<i>Sothahara, vishagna</i>
13	<i>Abhaya</i>	<i>Lavana varjita pancharasa</i>	<i>Laghu, ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha samaka</i>	<i>Kushtagna, sothahara, vranahara</i>
14	<i>Nilotpala</i>	<i>Kashaya, tikta, madhura</i>	<i>Laghu, snigdha, picchila</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Kaphapitta samaka</i>	<i>Rakthastambhana, vishagna, varnya</i>
15	<i>Sariva (sveta sariva)</i>	<i>Madhura, tikta</i>	<i>Guru, snigdha</i>	<i>sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosha hara</i>	<i>Raktasodhaka, dourgandhya nasaka</i>
16	<i>Siktha (madhucchista)</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
17	<i>Tutthaka (Tuttha)</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	<i>Taila (tila)</i>	<i>Madhura, tikta</i>	<i>Sukshma, guru, tikshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>katu</i>	<i>Vata pittahara</i>	<i>Swasakasahara, raktapitta hara</i>

Table no. 5: Phytoconstituents and pharmacological properties of *Jatyadi taila*.

Sl no	Drugs	Phytoconstituents	Pharmacological properties
1	<i>Jati</i>	Linalyl acetate, eugenol, resol	Antiseptic, anthelmintic, useful in odontalgia
2	<i>Nimba</i>	Nimbin, nimbinene, nimbandiol	Blood purifier, antidiabetic
3	<i>Patola</i>	Meso-inositol	febrifuge
4	<i>Naktamala (Karanja)</i>	Karanjin, pongapin, glabrin, kanjone	Antibacterial, insecticidal, wound healing
5	<i>Madhuka</i>	Glycyrrhizine, liquoric acid, licoagrone	Antimicrobial, antiviral, anti inflammatory
6	<i>Kushta</i>	Kushtin, inulin-betulin, sausrine	Antiseptic, antibacterial, bronchodilator
7	<i>Haridra</i>	Curcuminoids, camphene	Antioxidant, antimicrobial
8	<i>Daruharidra</i>	Berberine, berbamine	Stomachic, tonic

9	<i>Katurohini</i>	Picroside, kutkin	Anthelmintic, cholagogue
10	<i>Manjishtha</i>	Manjishtin, rubifolic acid	Blood purifier, anthelmintic
11	<i>Padmaka</i>	Padmakastein, beta sitosterol	Antibacterial, anti microbial, anti inflammatory
12	<i>Lodhra</i>	Triterpenoid, saponin, b-sitosterol	Haemostatic, anti inflammatory
13	<i>Abhaya</i>	Chebulagic acid, chebulic myrobalan	Antimicrobial, antifungal, antibacterial
14	<i>Nilotpala</i>	Nymphayol, quercetin, gallic acid	Astringent, cooling
15	<i>Sariva (sveta sariva)</i>	Resinic acid, tannins	demulcent
16	<i>Siktha(madhucchista)</i>	Myricyl palmitate, myricyl stearate	Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory
17	<i>Taila (tila)</i>	Cystine, histidine, riboflavin, leucine	Antioxidant, nematicidal

DISCUSSION

The standard *sneha kalpana* preparation ratio can be applied in this case, as water is used as the *dravadravya* in reference from the *Sharangadhara Samhita*. *Jatyadi taila* contains 18 ingredients including *tila taila*, seed and leaf of *karanja*, *Tutha* (mineral drug) and *madhucchista* etc. In this, *tutha* a mineral origin drug and *madhucchista* an animal origin drug should be added in *patrapaka*. *Patra paka* is the method used to enhance or flavour *Sneha* using specific substances. In this process, fine form of drugs were placed in a vessel, into which the *Sneha* is filtered in lukewarm state and then thoroughly mixed to ensure proper infusion. Certain substances such as waxes, gums, and resins can interfere with proper *paka*, if added too early. These ingredients dissolve quickly in hot oil, making the oil greasy and masking the *mridu*, *madhyama* and *khara paka* of *Sneha*. Additionally, they can complicate the straining process. For these reasons, it is better to add such substances as *patra paka*. On reviewing, it is noted that *Jati*, *Madhuka*, and *Haridra* were common ingredients in almost all references. From the above study, it was observed that most of the drugs have *Tikta Kashaya Madhura rasa*. *Tikta rasa dravyas* are known to cleanse wounds by removing toxins, pus, and infected materials and help to reduce microbial contamination due to their *krimighna* properties. It promotes granulation tissue formation and accelerates the healing process and supports cellular regeneration due to its subtle penetration. *Tikta rasa* pacifies *pitta* and *kapha doshas*, which are often involved in inflammation, infection, and delayed healing. *Kashaya rasa Dravya* helps to dry up exudate from the wound by absorbing excess moisture. Its astringent quality helps in drawing the edges of the wound together, aiding faster healing. *Jatyadi taila* is explained for external application in *vrana*. Ingredients

in *Jatyadi taila* like *Jati*, *nimba*, *haridra* etc have *vranahara* property. *Haridra* and *nimba* have proven antibacterial and antifungal properties. *Karanja*, *kushta*, *manjishta*, and *abhaya* have *sothahara* property. Almost all ingredients possess antibacterial, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties. All these together help in wound healing.

Two references are explained in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*, in *Mukha Roga* and *Vrana sotha*. Yoga Ratnakara also has two references, one in *sadhyovrana* and the other in *mukha roga*. *Gada nigraha* included *Jatyadi taila* in *taila prakarana* and *Upadamsa chikitsa*. In *Bhaishajya ratnavali mukha rogadhikara*, *acharya* mentioned about *loha choorna*, *sindoora* and *Swarna gairika* as ingredients and in the preparation of *taila*, include juice of *jati*, *sankupushpi*, and decoction of *bakula*. According to *Yogaratnakara mukha roga adhyaya*, *kashaya* is taken as the *drava Dravya*.

CONCLUSION

Upon reviewing all the available references of *Jatyadi taila*, it is evident that the ingredients listed by each Acharya vary, and the contexts in which the formulation is mentioned also differ. The main context in which *Jatyadi taila* is explained in the *Vrana* and *mukha roga adhyaya*. It includes the drugs having the property of *Tridosha samana*, which help to use in *vrana*, *upadamsa* and *mukha roga* conditions.

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